

IMPROVED FRACTURE MECHANICS PREDICTIONS FOR DELAMINATION OF COMPOSITES ACCOUNTING FOR YIELD ZONES

Z. Petrossian and Michael R. Wisnom

Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, Bristol, BS8 1TR, U.K.

SUMMARY: Analysis was carried out on a composite specimen containing discontinuous plies, previously tested in three-point bending. The locations of delaminations from the block of discontinuous plies were determined using the strain energy release rates from a finite element analysis. A mixed-mode failure criterion, based on the strain energy release rate, grossly overestimated the failure loads of the specimen under two different ratios of bending to out-of-plane shear loading. An improved approach, also based on the mixed-mode failure criterion but which took account of yielding in the resin at the onset of delamination, was able to predict the failure loads to within 3% of the experimental values.

KEYWORDS: delamination, fracture mechanics, strain energy release rate, finite element analysis, discontinuous plies, through thickness stress, plastic zone, initial defect

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced composite materials have lower transverse and interlaminar strengths compared to fibre-direction strengths. This means interlaminar failure can occur when the interlaminar stresses are much lower than the in-plane stresses. Significant interlaminar stresses can arise, for instance, at the ends of discontinuous plies. Such discontinuities are found in composite structures when plies are dropped off within a laminate to taper the thickness. Interlaminar shear stresses can arise when out-of-plane loading is applied to laminates. Helicopter rotor blades, aircraft wing boxes and floor beams are examples of structures susceptible to both out-of-plane loading and bending moments, which contain dropped plies. Bending moments cause local interlaminar stresses at discontinuous plies, and out-of-plane loading causes overall shear stresses. The combination of these two stress distributions can lead to cracks initiating at the ends of the discontinuous plies and propagating along the resin rich layers between the continuous and discontinuous plies. These cracks or delaminations can greatly reduce the strength and stiffness of the laminate, which in turn can lead to catastrophic failure of the whole structure. It is therefore very desirable to be able to predict the loading conditions at which delamination occurs.

Delamination is often predicted using the strain energy release rate, G . This approach was used to predict delamination from the free edges of laminates in [1]. Furthermore, G is usually calculated from finite element analysis via the virtual crack closure technique. This was done to investigate delamination from the ends of discontinuous plies in [2,3]. In [2] the laminates were in four-point bending and in [3] pure axial tension was applied. In [4] a stress based criterion was used to predict the initiation and location of damage in a composite specimen in

pure bending. Fracture mechanics was then used to predict the growth of delamination from the initial damage. Finally, in [5] fracture process zones at the free edge of laminates were taken into account. This enabled the initiation and growth of delamination to be predicted without any assumed initial defect.

In this paper, delamination from the ends of discontinuous plies is predicted with fracture mechanics taking into account the material yielding which occurs before crack propagation. The results of this improved approach are then compared to predictions which do not take account of the yielding, and to experimental data.

In [6] an account is given of the testing of straight unidirectional laminates in three-point bending, shown schematically in Fig. 1. The laminates consisted of 32 plies of E glass/ epoxy 913 and were nominally 10mm wide. Four of the plies near the tension surface were cut across the complete width. The bending moment caused local interlaminar stresses to arise around the cut. The shear force caused overall interlaminar shear stresses to arise in the section of the specimen between the loading rollers. The combination of these two stress distributions caused cracks to initiate at the cut and propagate along the interfaces of the continuous and cut plies, as seen in Fig. 1. Thus, specimen failure was due to delamination at the top left and bottom right of the cut. The ratio between the overall and local stresses was varied by changing the axial distance, d , between the cut and the central loading roller. The test results indicated a strong interaction between the two types of stress distributions. It was thought that this might be because the overall interlaminar shear stresses enlarged the zones of yielding in the resin rich layers between plies where the delaminations initiated.

When yielding occurs in the resin, the plies on either side are able to move relative to each other. Hence, strain energy can be released even when no physical crack is present. Thus, the larger the yield zone, the longer the effective crack length [7]. This is similar to the Irwin approach where the crack length is assumed to equal its physical length plus the length of the yield zone ahead of the crack tip. The yield zone length is estimated assuming linear-elastic material behaviour. His approach was developed for predicting crack propagation in metal plates with an initial crack. In this paper it is adapted for predicting delamination in composite laminates with no initial delamination.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of specimen with cut plies in three-point bending

The specimens described above are analysed. Two positions of the cut are studied; $d = 5\text{mm}$ and $d = 15\text{mm}$. A finite element model is created and the strain energy release rates of various

positions and combinations of cracks is evaluated. From the curves of G with respect to crack length, the locations of the cracks are predicted. The failure load is then predicted both with and without taking the yield zones into account. Both predictions are then compared to the experimental results.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

A two-dimensional finite element model was created using CPS4 elements in ABAQUS [8]. These are four-noded plane-stress elements. A plot of the mesh can be seen in Fig. 2, together with the boundary conditions corresponding to $d = 5\text{mm}$. For $d = 15\text{mm}$ the same model was used but the boundary conditions were moved left along the mesh by 10mm . Hence, the central loading point was slightly to the right of the centre of the model when $d = 5\text{mm}$, and slightly to the left when $d = 15\text{mm}$. This is exactly what was done during the tests. Since there were stress singularities present at the top and bottom of the cut a fine mesh was created around these two points. The mesh at the cut can be seen more clearly in Fig. 3. The cut is shown by the bold vertical line and four possible delamination paths are indicated with dashed horizontal lines. At the cut the elements are one ply thick and about 0.031mm long, and the length gradually increases moving away from the cut. There are dual coincident nodes along the possible crack interfaces and ends of the block of cut plies. During the testing of the specimens [6], the resin between the ends of the cut plies was seen to crack well before delamination occurred. Thus, the nodes on either side of the cut are not held together. Each pair of nodes along the crack interfaces is initially held together by one stiff spring acting in the horizontal direction and another acting in the vertical direction. This is to enable the virtual crack closure technique to be used. There are also gap elements along the interfaces to stop the two surfaces from crossing once the springs are removed.

Fig. 2: Finite Element Model with Boundary Conditions Corresponding to $d = 5\text{mm}$

A downward vertical concentrated load per unit width, P , is applied to the node at the point of contact of the central roller. The node at the point of contact of the left-hand roller is constrained to have zero x and z translation. The node at the point of contact of the roller on the right is constrained to have zero z translation. P is equal to the average experimental failure load per unit width. The value of P is 432.4 N/mm for $d = 15$ mm, and 284.0 N/mm for $d = 5$ mm. Refer to Table 1 for the material properties and dimensions of the model. The nominal value of the specimen thickness was initially assumed in the finite element analysis. From the corresponding results, the crack locations were determined. For the failure load predictions, it was deemed more accurate to use the average measured thickness of the specimens and to correct the axial Young's modulus for the lower fibre volume fraction. However, the change in the values of G were small enough not to affect the predicted crack locations.

Fig. 3: Close-Up of Mesh showing Cut and Possible Locations of Delaminations

Table 1: Material Properties and Dimensions.

Axial Young's Modulus, E_x , for Nominal Thickness	43.9 GPa
Axial Young's Modulus, E_x , for Measured Thickness	41.2 GPa
Through-Thickness Young's Modulus, E_z	15.4 GPa
Shear Modulus, G_{xz}	4.34 GPa
Poisson's Ratio, ν_{xz}	0.3
Length of Specimen	80 mm
Nominal Thickness	4 mm
Measured Thickness	4.33 mm
Width	10 mm
Distance between Outer Rollers	40 mm

DETERMINATION OF CRACK LOCATIONS BY TOTAL ENERGY APPROACH

The total strain energy release rate, G_T , was firstly found for individual cracks at each of the four possible crack locations, seen in Fig. 3. G_T was then found for cracks propagating simultaneously along all four crack paths, and finally for cracks propagating simultaneously along the top left and bottom right interfaces.

G_T was calculated from the change in total strain energy in the model as the crack was allowed to propagate by gradually removing the horizontal and vertical springs along the interfaces. This was done at each increment of crack length, a . The schematic definition of a is given in Fig. 1.

Graphs of G_T against a were plotted for all the cases and are given together in Fig. 4 for $d = 15\text{mm}$, and Fig. 5 for $d = 5\text{mm}$. It can be seen that in every case the value of G_T decreases with crack length until it reaches a minimum value, G_{\min} . After this, the value of G_T generally grows with crack length. This means, as the load is increased, the cracks will propagate in a stable manner up to a short crack length (corresponding to the minimum value of G_{\min}) and then crack propagation will be unstable. This behaviour was observed in the tests in [6]. Therefore, catastrophic failure occurs when G_{\min} reaches the critical value, G_c .

Fig. 4: Strain Energy Release Rate with Respect to Crack Length for Different Positions and Combinations of Cracks (Cut 15mm from Central Roller)

Fig. 5: Strain Energy Release Rate with Respect to Crack Length for Different Positions and Combinations of Cracks (Cut 5mm from Central Roller)

Since catastrophic failure depends on the value of G_{min} , the locations of the delaminations at failure can be determined by comparing the values of G_{min} corresponding to the different cases studied. The values of G_{min} are given in Table 2. Referring to the table, it is clear that for $d = 15\text{mm}$ the most likely type of failure is by delaminations propagating simultaneously from the top left and bottom right of the cut, since the value of G_{min} is the highest for this situation. For the $d = 5\text{mm}$ case, G_{min} is highest when a crack propagates from the bottom right corner only. However, cracks from both the bottom right and top left of the cut were observed in the tests.

Although cracking is primarily mode II due to the type of loading, a small amount of mode I is generally present. Furthermore, the difference between the values of G_{min} for cracking at the bottom right only, and simultaneous cracking at the bottom right and top left is not very great. Thus, the fact that cracking occurred simultaneously at the bottom right and top left, even when the value of G_T was lower in the $d = 5\text{mm}$ case, can be explained by more mode I being present. It was therefore concluded that the mode ratio would have to be taken into account for accurately predicting the failure loads.

Table 2: Minimum Values of G_T for Various Cracks (From Figures 4 and 5)

	d = 15mm	d = 5mm
Crack at Top Left Only	0.34 N/mm	0.67 N/mm
Crack at Top Right Only	0.00 N/mm	0.00 N/mm
Crack at Bottom Right Only	0.39 N/mm	1.03 N/mm
Crack at Bottom Left Only	0.00 N/mm	0.00 N/mm
Cracks at All Locations	0.23 N/mm	0.63 N/mm
Cracks at Bottom Right & Top Left	0.45 N/mm	0.93 N/mm

FAILURE LOAD PREDICTION USING STANDARD MIXED MODE APPROACH

Cracks were assumed to propagate simultaneously (and at the same rate) along the top left and bottom right interfaces, for both cut positions. The following mixed-mode criterion was used to predict the failure loads:

$$G_I / G_{Ic} + G_{II} / G_{IIc} = 1 \tag{1}$$

where G_I and G_{II} are the mode I and mode II components of the strain energy release rate, respectively, and G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} are their critical values. For E glass/ epoxy 913, $G_{Ic} = 0.25$ N/mm and $G_{IIc} = 1.08$ N/mm, [9].

G_I and G_{II} , were found with respect to the crack length, a , using the virtual crack closure technique. This assumes the strain energy released when a crack propagates is equal to the energy required to close the crack. G_I was calculated from the spring forces and relative nodal displacements in the vertical (z) direction, and G_{II} was calculated from the spring forces and relative nodal displacements in the horizontal (x) direction. G_I and G_{II} were then each normalised by their corresponding critical values.

The graphs of normalised G against a for the two cut positions ($d = 15\text{mm}$ and $d = 5\text{mm}$) can be seen in Figures 6 and 7. One can see the sum of the normalised strain energy release rates, $(G_I/G_{Ic} + G_{II}/G_{IIc})$, decreases to a minimum value as the cracks start propagating. Then, after a crack length between 0.2mm to 0.3mm , the value starts to increase again. As explained in the previous section, this means the load at catastrophic failure is governed by the minimum value of $(G_I/G_{Ic} + G_{II}/G_{IIc})$. At the average experimental failure loads, the minimum values of $(G_I/G_{Ic} + G_{II}/G_{IIc})$ are 0.61 for the $d = 15\text{mm}$ case, and 0.83 for the $d = 5\text{mm}$ case. Thus, according to Eqn 1, both the predicted failure loads are higher than the experimental failure loads. The strain energy release rate is proportional to the square of the applied load, so the predicted failure loads per unit width are:

$$P = 553 \text{ N/mm} \quad \text{for } d = 15\text{mm}$$

and

$$P = 312 \text{ N/mm} \quad \text{for } d = 5\text{mm}.$$

Fig. 6: Normalised Strain Energy Release Rate at Experimental Failure Load (Cut 15mm from Central Roller)

Fig. 7: Normalised Strain Energy Release Rate at Experimental Failure Load (Cut 5mm from Central Roller)

IMPROVED FAILURE LOAD PREDICTION

The axial distance from the cut to which the zones of yielding material extended was estimated from the finite element analysis. This was done at the top left and bottom right of the cut. The resin along the interfaces of the cut and continuous plies was assumed to yield when the interlaminar shear stress exceeded 70 MPa. This value was estimated from the measured in-plane shear stress-strain response of glass/ epoxy $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens in tension [10], and assuming transverse isotropy. The yield zone length at the top left was averaged with the length at the bottom right. This was the effective initial crack length. The corresponding value of $(G_I/G_{Ic} + G_{II}/G_{IIc})$ was found by interpolation. If the value of $(G_I/G_{Ic} + G_{II}/G_{IIc})$ was less than one at the effective initial crack length, it meant the predicted failure load was higher than the experimental failure load, and vice versa. If this was the case, the value of $(G_I/G_{Ic} + G_{II}/G_{IIc})$ and the yield zone lengths were recalculated at higher (or lower) values of P . No further finite element calculations were necessary since the shear stress was proportional to P , and the value of $(G_I/G_{Ic} + G_{II}/G_{IIc})$ was proportional to P^2 . After a small number of iterations, the predicted failure load converged. The values for $d = 5\text{mm}$ and $d = 15\text{mm}$ are given in Table 3, alongside the previous predictions and the average experimental values. The values of the yield zone lengths in the $d = 5\text{mm}$ case were 0.70 mm at the top left and 0.48 mm at the bottom right of the cut. The values for $d = 15\text{mm}$ were 1.57 mm at the top left and 0.38 mm at the bottom right. Although there was a big difference between the latter values, averaging them together was considered to be the best solution for the purposes of keeping the approach manageable.

Note that both the strain energy release rate and the yield zone lengths were calculated assuming linear-elastic material properties. The estimated yield zone lengths would be longer if non-linear stress-strain behaviour was taken into account. However, the strain energy release rate would be lower since yielding limits the stresses at the crack tip. Thus, to some degree these two effects cancel each other out. Also, to accurately predict the yield zone length and corresponding strain energy release rate, the resin along the interfaces would have to be modelled using non-linear material properties. This would require much more computational time, and for the purpose of engineering design, the approach used above is thought to be reasonable.

Table 3: Failure loads (per unit width)

	d = 15mm	d = 5mm
Experimental Average	432.4 N/mm	284.0 N/mm
Prediction (Standard Mixed-Mode)	553 N/mm	312 N/mm
Prediction (Including Yield Zones)	444 N/mm	280 N/mm

DISCUSSION

The analysis showed that when no account is taken of yielding, linear-elastic fracture mechanics is not able to accurately predict delamination in laminates with significant overall interlaminar shear stresses. Referring to Table 3, it can be seen that the failure loads predicted without accounting for yielding at the onset of delamination are both very unconservative. The prediction for the d = 15mm case is 28% higher than the experimental value, and the prediction for the d = 5mm case is 10% higher. The prediction corresponding to the d = 15mm case is worse because the ratio between the shear force and the bending moment is higher when the cut is further from the central roller. Hence, the relative importance of the overall interlaminar shear stress is greater, and the yield zones are generally longer when d = 15mm. When the improved approach is applied to the two cases, the predictions are within 3% of the experimental results. Therefore, the improved approach was able to accurately predict the failure loads of laminates with two different levels of yielding.

Previously it was found that a linear interaction equation between the effects of overall interlaminar shear stresses and local stresses at the cut gave a good prediction of failure [6]. The results presented here explain the interaction in terms of the increased effective crack length as the overall interlaminar shear stresses become high compared with the yield stress.

CONCLUSIONS

A composite specimen containing cut plies under three-point bending was analysed. The ratio between the bending moment and the shear force at the cut was varied by changing the position of the cut relative to the applied loads. The strain energy release rate was calculated for delaminations spreading from the cut using finite element analysis. A mixed-mode failure criterion, based on the strain energy release rate, grossly overestimated the failure loads for both cut positions. An improved approach, also based on the mixed-mode failure criterion but which took account of yielding in the resin at the onset of delamination, was able to predict

the failure loads to within 3% of the experimental values. This shows the importance of considering the yielding that occurs before crack formation when predicting delamination in laminates under high overall interlaminar shear stresses.

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